

Research Productivity of BLDEA's Professional Institutes of Vijayapura: A Bibliometric Study

* Dr M.M.Bachalapur, Librarian, BLDEA's V P Dr P.G.Halakatti College of Engineering and Technology, Vijayapura, bachalapur@gmail.com, <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2402-2477>

**Dr Prasanna Kumar B.M, University Librarian, BLDE (Deemed to be University), Vijayapura, bm.prasanna@bldedu.ac.in, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2760-443X>
(Corresponding Author)

***Dr. Jayaprakash G. Hugar, Librarian, Dnyanprassarak Mandal's College and Research Centre, Assagao, Bardez, Mapusa, Goa,, dmclibrarian@rediffmail.com, <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8307-5582>

Abstract:

This paper attempts to assess the research trend and productivity of BLDEA's professional institutes in Vijayapura under the banner of BLDE Association's based on their publications as reflected in the Scopus Citation Database for the period of ten years from 2011 to 2020. A total of 910 research publications with all metadata have been downloaded and analyzed as per the objectives of the current study. The paper tries to give all dimensions to a view of the research output of BLDEA's professional institutes in the health sciences and engineering and technology domain. BLDEA's professional institutes have published 733 articles, 85 conference papers and, 37 reviews papers. Prof. Kusal K.Das of BLDE (DU), Prof Kulkarni R V of BLDEA's SSM Pharmacy college and Prof. Pushpa B.Patil of BLDEACET are top publishers of the articles in the Scopus citation database during the study period 2011-2020.

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, BLDEA's, Vijayapura, Scopus, Research, Productivity, Research Impact.

Introduction:

Bijapur Lingayat District Educational Association has a big name and fame in the education sector, especially in northern Karnataka, established in 1910. It has three major professional institutes and provides quality education in the health sciences and engineering education in the north part of Karnataka. These three institutes have vibrant research publications in health science and technical education, as reflected in various publications. The research productivity of these institutions is noticeable and recognized in their respective domain.

Scope and Limitation of the Study:

The scope of this study covers the research productivity of BLDEA's professional colleges of Vijayapura BLDE (Deemed to be University), BLDEA's Shri Sanganabasava Mahaswamiji College of Pharmacy and Research Centre and BLDEA's V P Dr P.G.Halakatti College of Engineering and Technology, which has been reflected in Scopus Citation Database and we have chosen for the period between 2011 to 2020.

Methodology:

The source for data collection is the Scopus Citation Database. Affiliation ID's of the respective institutes is used for the search and download of the published materials. It includes the "BLDE (Deemed to be University)" Scopus Affiliation ID: 60109280 , "BLDEA'S VP Dr. P G Halakatti College of Engineering and Technology" Scopus Affiliation ID: 60097448, and " Shri Sanganabasava Mahaswamiji College of Pharmacy & Research Centre" Scopus Affiliation ID: 60113717, the individual years starting from 2011 to 2020. Each of the records collects data items included author(s), title, document types like articles, proceedings papers, notes, meeting abstracts, reviews, letters, editorial materials, news items, about an individual and biographical item-all indexing term used in the source database for categorizing the published materials, language, institution and year of publication. The Biblioshiny Software is used for Bibliometric analysis, and average also applied apart from the above statistical tools.

Objectives:

The study's objectives aimed to evaluate the trend of research productivity of BLDEA's professional colleges based on documents indexed in the Scopus Citation Database by analyzing the following features of publications during the study period.

1. To analyze year-wise annual scientific production of BLDEA's professional institutes.
2. To know the most prolific authors.
3. To analyze different type of documents.
4. To recognize the most productive journals.
5. To understand the collaborative study of BLDEA's professional institutes.

Review of Literature:

Sumit Kumar Bansal and others (2017) analyzed the data indexed in Web of Science for all the 16 IITs to identify productivity, productivity per capita, research output growth rate, authorship, collaboration pattern, citation, citation, citation, and citation impact and discipline-wise research strengths of the different IITs. The research performances of the IITs have been compared with those of two top-ranking engineering and technology institutions of the world (MIT-USA and NTU-Singapore), and most cited papers from these IITs have also been identified. (Sumit Kumar Bansal, Vivek Kumar Singh*, AparnaBasu and Pranab Kumar Muhuri 2017)

Satish Kumar (2020) analyzed the research productivity of the Indian Institute of Technology (ISM) Dhanbad for a period of twenty years during 2000-2019. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the research performance of IIT (ISM) Dhanbad. Required data is taken from the Web of Science (WoS) bibliographical database. Further analysis was done with various prospects to know the high prolific authors and areas of research interest. Six thousand nine hundred sixty-two research papers have been published over 20 years in which 5,201 research publications are in referred research journals, and the rest of the research publications are in conferences, symposiums, bulletins, reviews etc. The paper reveals the total research productivity of the institution quantitatively in terms of the number of articles, citations, collaboration, h-index, source journals etc. Findings also indicate the publication pattern, degree of collaboration, and the nature of the research activities carried out. (Kumar, Satish, 2020)

Suresh, N and Thanuskodi, S (2019): analyzed the research output of ICAR- Indian Institute of Horticulture, Bangalore (ICAR-IIHR) from 1989 to 2018. The authors examined the growth and development of the research activity of ICAR-IIHR as reflected in publications output in the web of science database. Data for the study is a total of 1095 records have been downloaded and analyzed according to objectives. The study reveals that the growth of literature follows the exponential growth pattern, journal articles are the most published form of literature (90.13%), Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences followed by Current Science are top journals, the United States and Horticultural experiment Station are top collaborating country and institutions respectively. The highly productive subject areas are Agriculture and Plant Sciences. Collaborating authorship pattern analysis shows that

degree of collaboration (90%) significantly high. Overall, the paper presents an informed account of ICAR-IIHR's research performance (N, SURESH and s, ThanuskodiDr, 2019)

Priyambada Das and D.B. Ramesh (2019) studied scholarly communication of three leading countries in pharmaceutical research as reflected in the SCOPUS database during 1998-2017. In terms of publication output, the United States, with two leading Asian countries, China and India, leads with a 40.54 percent share of the global research publication share in pharmaceutical sciences. The global outcome of scholarly communication in the field of pharmaceutical research is 13,95,221. The study mainly focuses on qualitative and quantitative research growth of the United States, China and India in terms of output of scholarly communication, citation impact, relative research effort, familiar sources used for publications and research collaboration. The comparative research effort of India and China increased during 2008-2017, while in the United States, it was decreased. Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry, Tetrahedron Letters and Tetrahedron are familiar communication sources in these three countries. All three countries show a positive shift in international collaboration during 1998-2002 to 2012-2017 in pharmaceutical research.(Priyambada Das and D.B. Ramesh, 2019)

Chaman Sab M, Dharani Kumar P and BS Biradar (2019) Analyzed the Indian publications output in Pharmacology and Pharmacy during 2004-18 on several parameters including contribution and citation impact of most productive countries, India's overall contribution, its growth pattern, citation impact, the share of international collaboration, identification of significant participating countries in India's international cooperation, most productivity and impact of leading Indian institutions and authors. The Web of Science Citation Database has been used to retrieve 15 years (2004-18) data for by searching the keywords "Pharmacology and Pharmacy" in the combined Title, Abstract and Keywords field. The Indian publications output in Pharmacology and Pharmacy research consisted of 37,734 papers during 2004-18. Indian research output on Pharmacology and Pharmacy is relatively low globally, as reflected from its publication output per thousand publications (0.001) and its world publication share (3.28%) during 2004 – 2018. They have also identified the impact and quality of Indian research is low compared to select development and developing countries. (Chaman Sab M, Dharani Kumar P, B. S. Biradar, 2019)

Sadik Batcha, M (2017) assessed the volume of research carried out by the scientists worldwide on robotic technology, their share of research to world literature in robotics, forms

and language that they publish their results, quantum of their publications in terms of institutions involved in research in robotic technology, extent of international collaboration, etc. Data for this study was picked from the Web of Science. The study period is from 1990 to 2016. Totally 3703 institutions resulted in the output of 5316 among them; top 30 institutions' production is noteworthy. The developing countries like the USA, UK and Germany concentrate in the field of robotic technology. Yet Major portion of the contribution (36.30%) is from the USA. The journal articles are the key factors in sharing the research values among the researchers in the forms of essays that amounted to be top (67.40%). The language preferred in exchanging research results is English (87.70%), followed by German. The prolific authors in the field of robotic technology are highly found in the USA. Among them, the contribution by Bloss R is appreciable. The citation counts seem to be high in the year 2015, which has recorded 11,000 citations. (M.SadikBatcha, 2017)

Based on the above literature, we found that no such comparison has been made until now, which compared the scholarly output and impact of education society in Karnataka. We have attempted to research this direction to determine the annual growth rate and citation pattern of the BLDEA's (DU), Pharmacy and Engineering Colleges in Bijapur during 2011-2020.

Data Analysis and Discussion:

Table No. 1: Year wise Distribution of Publications

Year	BLDE (DU)		BLDEA's SSM		BLDEACET	
	No of Articles	Percentage of Publication	No of Articles	Percentage of Publication	No of Articles	Percentage of Publication
2011	35	5.60	19	19.59	13	6.95
2012	57	9.10	18	18.56	7	3.74
2013	83	13.26	14	14.43	11	5.88
2014	64	10.22	5	5.15	5	2.67
2015	78	12.46	5	5.15	7	3.74
2016	69	11.02	9	9.28	13	6.95
2017	69	11.02	7	7.22	26	13.91
2018	51	8.15	4	4.12	30	16.05
2019	62	9.90	7	7.22	33	17.65
2020	58	9.27	9	9.28	42	22.46
	626	100	97	100	187	100

Figure No. 1: Annual Scientific Production

Table 1 displays the publication trend of all the three institutions of the Bijapur Lingayath Districts Educational Association’s Society, Bijapur. Overall, BLDE (Deemed to be University) published 626 publications during the last ten years from 2011 to 2020 and stood 1st rank, followed by 187 publications of BLDEACET and 97 publications of Pharmacy College ranked 2nd 3rd place respective in publication. The highest numbers of publications are published in 2013 by the Deemed University, from Pharmacy College in 2011 and 2020 by the BLDEACET.

The lowest numbers of publications are published in the initial year 2011 in all the professional colleges. These institutes publish an average of 91 publications. From 2011 to 2020, BLDE (DU) has published on an average 62 publications per year; at the same time, 18 is the average number of publications of Engineering College, and in the pharmacy college, it is ten publications per year.

Table No.2: Distribution of Type of Publications

BLDE (DU)		BLDEA’s SSM		BLDEACET	
Article	558	Article	88	Article	87
Review	25	Review	7	Review	5
Book Chapter	8	Book Chapter	1	Book Chapter	14
Letter	20	Editorial	1	Retracted	1
Conference Paper	5			Conference Paper	80
Note	8				
Editorial	1				
Short Survey	1				
Total	626		97		187

Table 2 shows that distribution of different types of publications; BLDE (DU) has 626 publications. The highest 558 publications gone to journal articles, 25 review papers, 20 letters and book chapter 08 and only 5 conference papers and each one short survey and editorial appeared during the study period. BLDEA's SSM has 97 publications, of which 88 publications are of journal articles, seven publications are reviews, book chapters, and editorials are each publication during the study period. Eighty-seven publications belonged to journal articles, conference papers 80, book chapter 14, review papers 5 and retraced paper 1, a totally of 187 publications are published during the study period by the BLDEACET.

Further from this table, it is known that researchers are showing more interest in article publications rather than any other type of publications, it is interesting to note that BLDEA's SSM College has fewer publications of 97 compared to the other two professional colleges, but within 97 publications, a maximum number of publications are in the form of articles (88). It shows that Researchers has given much importance to articles publications rather than any other forms.

Overall, in all the three institutions, article's publications (733) is more, compared to any other forms such as Conference Paper (85) and Reviews (37) have got top priority by the authors and remaining type of publications such as Letter, Note, Editorial, Short Survey, Retracted and another type of publications are very less.

Table No. 3: Most prolific authors and impact of their output

Authors	Total No. of Publications	Total No. of Citations	Citations per paper	Relative Citation Index	Institutions
Das, K.K.	58 (23.67)	1368(20.60)	23.89	0.87	BLDE DU)
Inamadar, A.C.	42(17.14)	805(12.12)	19.17	0.70	BLDE DU)
Palit, A.	35(14.28)	762(11.47)	21.77	0.80	BLDE DU)
Kulkarni, R.V.	34(13.87)	1240(18.68)	36.47	1.34	BLDEA's SSM
Kalyane, N.V.	21(8.57)	228(3.43)	10.86	0.40	BLDEA's SSM
Hugar, S.	10(4.08)	141(2.12)	14.1	0.51	BLDEA's SSM
Patil, P.B.	17(6.93)	39(0.58)	2.29	0.08	BLDEACET
Das, S.N.	15(6.12)	687(10.34)	45.8	1.68	BLDEACET
Das, K.K.	13(5.30)	1368(20.60)	105.23	3.88	BLDEACET

Table 3 shows BLDEA's most prolific authors research productivity, the research productivity of top 9 most productive authors varied from 13 to 58 publications.

Nine authors registered publications output above the group average of 27.22: Das KK (58 papers), Inamdar AC (42 papers) and Patil A (35 papers), Kulkarni RV (34

papers), Kalyane NV (21 papers), Hugar S (10 papers), Patil PB (17 papers), Das SN (15 papers), once again Das KK (13 papers) as a co-author with the BLDEACET during the period of study.

Only Das SN and Das KK has received more than average (31.06) citations per paper in this list of most prolific authors

The Relative Citation Index (RCI) is a new metric, based on weighting the number of citations a paper receives to a comparison group within the same field. Three authors registered the relative citation index above the group average (1.14) of all authors, highest relative citation index is of Das KK with 3.88 and lowest is of 0.08 with Patil PB both are from BLDEACET during the study period.

Table No. 4: Most Preferred Journals of BLDEA's Institutions

Title of the Journals	Total Publications	Total Citations	h-Index	IF	Country	Professional Institutes
Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research	86	286	47	0.63	India	BLDE (DU)
Journal of Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences University	83	234	10	1.5	India	BLDE (DU)
Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research	32	81	29	0.41	India	BLDE (DU)
International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences	34	64	29	0.88	India	BLDE (DU)
Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development	23	17	18	0.87	India	BLDE (DU)
Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology	10	13	46	0.34	India	BLDEA's SSM
International Journal of Biological Macromolecules	5	182	128	5.16	Netherlands	BLDEA's SSM
Pharmacology Online	5	11	25	0.31	Italy	BLDEA's SSM
Indian Drugs	3	6	31	0.14	India	BLDEA's SSM
Journal of Microbiological Methods	3	50	133	1.70	Netherlands	BLDEA's SSM
Communications In Computer and Information Science	8	6	51	0.48	Germany	BLDEACET
Journal of Basic and Clinical Physiology and Pharmacology	4	66	33	1.69	Germany	BLDEACET
Advances In Intelligent Systems and Computing	3	3	41	0.63	Germany	BLDEACET
AIP Conference Proceedings	3	0	75	0.40	USA	BLDEACET

The above table displays the most preferred journals by the BLDEA's authors, total number of publications in a particular journal and citations received by it, followed by their

impact factor, h-index of these journals along with the place of publication is shown in table No. 4. Journal of clinical and diagnostic research produced the highest number of publications and received highest number of total citations, but its h-index and Impact Factor is low compared to any other journals. By producing 83 publications and received 234 citations during the study period, Journal of Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences University is the second topmost journal, but its h-index and Impact Factor are also low.

Journal h-index is one measure of the quality of a journal and can be calculated using data from Scopus or Google Scholar. In this study, the Journal of Microbiological Methods got an h-index of 133, which is the highest in this list of journals, followed by the International Journal of Biological Macromolecules with an h-index of 128.

The Impact Factor (IF) measures the frequency with which the average article in a journal has been cited in a particular year. It is used to measure the importance or rank by calculating the times its articles are cited. Here we found BLDEA's SSM published article journal has the highest and lowest Impact Factor in the International Journal of Biological Macromolecules with 5.16 and the lowest is of 0.14 of the Indian Drugs journal.

More than 46% of the journals are published from India in these top 14 journals, followed by Germany and Netherlands. Each journal is listed in the above table from USA and Italy also. It is interesting to know that all the top 5 journals of BLDE (DU) are published from India, whereas; BLDEA's SSM articles are published in India, Netherlands and Italy. BLDEACET articles published more in Germany.

Table No. 5: Productivity of Authors

Documents written	BLDE (DU)		BLDEA SSM		BLDEACET	
	No. of Authors	Proportion of Authors	No. of Authors	Proportion of Authors	No. of Authors	Proportion of Authors
1	1044	0.343	145	0.69	188	0.686
2	188	0.062	31	0.148	42	0.153
3	85	0.028	13	0.062	12	0.044
4	750	0.246	4	0.019	5	0.018
5	592	0.194	4	0.019	7	0.026
6	298	0.098	3	0.014	5	0.018
7	15	0.005	2	0.01	5	0.018
8	14	0.005	3	0.014	2	0.007
9	16	0.005	2	0.01	2	0.007
10	15	0.005	1	0.005	1	0.004
11	4	0.001	1	0.005	2	0.007

12	4	0.001	1	0.005	1	0.004
13	6	0.002	-	-	1	0.004
14	3	0.001	-	-	1	0.004
15	4	0.001	-	-	-	-
16	1	0	-	-	-	-
19	1	0	-	-	-	-
20	2	0.001	-	-	-	-
23	2	0.001	-	-	-	-
24	1	0	-	-	-	-

The highest number of authors together written single article is more in BLDE (DU) than in all the three institutions of BLDEA.

The bibliometric analysis of the 239 papers showed that, from this period, 327 different authors published papers (0.731 documents per author). But the author's appearances were 454 (authors per document 1.37)

The bibliometric analysis of the 626 articles showed that, from this period, 3045 different authors published papers (0.205 documents per author).

The 626 articles were authored by 3045 authors, among them 1044 (0.343) authors contributed to only one article, 188 (0.062) authors contributed to two articles, 85 (0.028) authors contributed to three articles. Whereas, 750 (0.246) authors contributed to four articles, 592 (0.194) contributed to five articles, and 298 (0.098) contributed to six articles. Additionally, 59 articles were single-authored publications, 43 articles written by two authors, 14 articles authored by three authors, 38 articles written by four authors, 17 articles had fifteen authors, 9 articles had sixteen authors, and 8 articles had fourteen authors.

Fifty-nine individual authors have published single-authored publications (with few of them publishing more than one single-authored publication), and 567 authors contributed to multi-authored publications. These data reveal that over 90% of the authors conducted their research collaboratively with different individuals, organizations, nations and written papers.

Table No. 6: Country wise Collaboration of Publications

BLDE (DU)		BLDEA's SSM		BLDEACET	
Region	No. of Publications	Region	No. of Publications	Region	No. of Publications
India	1817	India	234	India	397
Iran	1230	Australia	11	South Africa	4

USA	905	South Korea	2	Australia	3
Australia	524	Thailand	1	South Korea	3
UK	463	USA	1	UK	2
Ethiopia	388	-	-	USA	2
China	216	-	-	Myanmar	1
Canada	209	-	-	Poland	1
Italy	209	-	-	-	-
Brazil	170	-	-	-	-
Nigeria	170	-	-	-	-
Pakistan	128	-	-	-	-
Germany	124	-	-	-	-
Saudi Arabia	117	-	-	-	-
South Africa	115	-	-	-	-
Egypt	105	-	-	-	-
Spain	95	-	-	-	-
Mexico	89	-	-	-	-
Romania	88	-	-	-	-
Sweden	88	-	-	-	-

Table 6 shows the collaboration work of different organization authors with the BLDEA institutions in different countries all over the world. It shows that Collaboration with Indian Authors is more compared to any other countries during the study period, in all the three institutions.

It is very interesting to know that, BLDE (DU) authors have collaboratively written 7041 publications with 19 countries such as Iran, USA, Australia, UK, Ethiopia, China, Canada, Italy, Brazil, Nigeria, Pakistan, Germany, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Egypt, Spain, Mexico, Romania and Sweden. On average, 370 publications have collaborated with these 19 countries.

Pharmacy College authors are collaborated with four different countries, such as Australia, South Korea, Thailand and the USA. Pharmacy college authors do not collaborate with foreign countries; only 15 publications have collaborated with the countries mentioned above. Whereas, 234 articles are collaborated with the different authors in India.

Sixteen collaborative publications are published with the authors of the BLDEACET with seven countries such as South Africa, Australia, South Korea, UK, USA, Myanmar and Poland. 397 publications are published by collaborating Indian authors in BLDEACET.

Table No. 7: Funding Agency wise Distribution of Publications

BLDE (DU)	BLDEA's SSM	BLDEACET
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National Institutes of Health, Maryland USA	8	Board of Research in Nuclear Sciences	2	All India Council for Technical Education	3
Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development	6	Bhabha Atomic Research Centre	2	Defense Research and Development Organisation	3
Wellcome Trust	6	Defence Science and Technology Group	2	Ministry of Defense	3
Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation	5	Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences	2	Department of Science and Technology, Government of Kerala	2
Deakin University	5	Chulalongkorn University	1	Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India	1
European Commission	5	Defence Research and Development Organisation	1	Indian Council of Agricultural Research	1
Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology	5	Department of Atomic Energy, Government of India	1	Lamar University	1
National Heart Foundation of Australia	5	Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University	1	Science and Engineering Research Board	1
Arizona State University	4	Department of Science and Technology, Government of West Bengal	1	Vision Group on Science and Technology	1
Chief Scientist Office, Scottish Government Health and Social Care Directorate	4	Generalitat de Catalunya	1	Visvesvaraya Technological University	1

Funding sponsors wise distribution of publications is revealed in table 7. National Institute of Health sponsored eight publications, followed by Eunice Kennedy Shiver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development and Welcome Trust sponsored every six publications during the study period in the BLDE (DU).

In the Pharmacy College, the highest publications of 2 each received sponsorship from the Board of Research in Nuclear Sciences, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Defense Science and Technology Group and Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences. Another five funding agencies sponsored five publications during the study period.

BLDEACET got sponsorship from the AICTE, DRDO and Ministry of Defence sponsored every three publications, Department of Science and Technology, Govt. Of Kerala Sponsored two publications, Department of Science and Technology Government of India, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Lamar University, Science and Engineering

Research Board, Vision Group on Science and Technology and Visvesvaraya Technological University sponsored each one publication during the period of study.

Table No. 8: Top 15 Collaborations of BLDEA's Institutions

Top Collaborating Institutes	Articles	Country	Professional Colleges
Visvesvaraya Technological University	29	India	BLDEACET
BLDE Deemed to be University	28	India	BLDEA's SSM
Shri Sanganabasava Mahaswamiji College of Pharmacy and Research Centre	28	India	BLDE (DU)
Basaveshwar Engineering College	25	India	BLDEACET
Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences Deemed University	24	India	BLDE (DU)
J.J.M. Medical College	23	India	BLDE (DU)
Al-Ameen Medical College	17	India	BLDE (DU)
Emory University	15	Georgia	BLDE (DU)
BLDE Deemed to be University	14	India	BLDEACET
Manipal College of Pharmaceutical Sciences	9	India	BLDEA's SSM
The University of Sydney	8	Australia	BLDEA's SSM
JAIN Deemed-to-be University	7	India	BLDEA's SSM
Jadavpur University	7	India	BLDEA's SSM
Kuvempu University	6	India	BLDEACET
Al-Ameen Medical College	6	India	BLDEACET

The top 15 research collaborations of BLDEA's institutions with the other national and international organizations/institutions are shown in table 8. The highest collaboration of BLDEACET institutions is with Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU) with 29 publications, followed by Basaveshwar Engineering College having the collaboration of 25 articles and BLDE (DU) is 14 articles.

BLDEA's SSM, the highest collaboration is found with BLDE (DU) having 28 articles and then, Manipal College of Pharmaceutical Sciences with 9 and 8 publications with the University of Sydney from Australia.

BLDE (DU) collaborates with the BLDEA's SSM (28), followed by 24 articles with Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences Deemed University and JJM Medical College at Davanagere 23 publications during the study period.

Only BLDE (DU) and BLDEA's SSM is having collaboration with foreign institutions. On average, 16.4 articles are in collaboration found in this study, and only seven institutions collaborated with BLDEA's professional institutions.

Findings:

1. It shows that the highest number of publications are started appearing in the year 2011 by the pharmacy college faculties, then raised in the year 2013 by the Deemed University and ended up with the BLDEACET faculty members as highest producers of publications during the study period. These institutions publish an average of 91 publications.
2. On average, 63 citations are received per year in the last ten years in BLDE (DU). In the Pharmacy college, an average of ten citations per year received by the 97 publications. On average, four citations per year received by the 187 publications during the study period in BLDEACET.
3. Overall, in all the institutions, the article's publications (733) are more, and then come to Conference Paper (85), and Reviews (37) have got top priority by the authors.
4. Das KK of BLDE (DU), Kulkarni RV of Pharmacy College and Patil PB of BLDEACET are at the forefront of publishing the articles in the Scopus database during the study period.
5. More authors from BLDE (DU) published their research publications in the Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research. Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology is the top journal found by the Pharmacy College authors. Communications in Computer and Information Science is the leading journal for the authors of BLDEACET for their research articles publications.
6. Highest number of author's have collaboration with foreign countries is found in the BLDE (DU) and fewer numbers in Pharmacy College.
7. The highest number of collaborations with foreign countries is found in the BLDE (DU), followed by BLDEACET, and less cooperation is found in the SSM Pharmacy College.

Conclusion:

The present bibliometric analysis of BLDEA's professional institutes reveals that the total number of publications of these three BLDEA's professional institutes is 910 and, the majority of research publication is found in health sciences and followed by engineering science and technology between 2011-2020, as the data is reflected in the Scopus citation databases. It is observed steady growth from 2011 onwards in terms of publications, and the total citations received by three institutes is 4247. The h-Index of these three institutes are

good BLDE (DU)-30, BLDEA's SSM -21, and BLDEACET-16. It clearly shows that publications are increasing, and the research productivity of these institutes is progressive. BLDE (DU) and BLDEA's SSM Pharmacy College having, collaborated with foreign institutions.

Acknowledgement:

The Authors of this paper is gratefully expressing their acknowledgement to BLDE Association, Vijayapur and BLDEA's group of professional institutes.

REFERENCES:

1. Banshal, S. K., Singh, V. K., Basu, A., & Muhuri, P. K. (2017). Research performance of Indian Institutes of Technology. *Current Science*, *112*(5), 923–932. <https://doi.org/10.18520/cs/v112/i05/923-932>
2. Batcha, M. (2017). Research Output Analysis on Robotic Technology: A Scientometric Study Library Management View project Research Output Analysis on Robotic Technology: A Scientometric Study. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*.
3. *BLDE(Deemed to be University) – Inspiring Generations*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 3, 2021, from <https://bldedu.ac.in/>
4. *BLDEA - History - BLDE Association - In the year 1942, a religious leader*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 3, 2021, from <https://www.bldea.org/about/>
5. Das, P., & Ramesh, D. B. (2019). Trends in pharmaceutical scholarly communications from India, China and United States: A comparative study. *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology*, *39*(5), 230–237. <https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.39.5.14602>
6. *Home - BLDE College of Pharmacy and Research Center*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 3, 2021, from <http://www.bldeapharmacy.ac.in/>
7. *Home - BLDEACET*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 3, 2021, from <http://bldeacet.ac.in/>
8. Karpagam, R. (2014). Global research output of nanobiotechnology research: A scientometrics study. *Current Science*, *106*(11), 1490–1499. <https://doi.org/10.18520/cs/v106/i11/1490-1499>
9. Kumar, S. (2020). Scientometric analysis of research productivity of IIT(ISM) Dhanbad. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, *2020*(September), 1–18.
10. Sab, C., Dharani Kumar, P., & Biradar, B. S. (2019). Marketing research in India: A scientometrics study. *Webology*, *16*(2), 172–186. <https://doi.org/10.14704/web/v16i2/a197>
11. *Scopus - Document search | Signed in*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 3, 2021, from <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=basic#basic>
12. Suresh, N., & Thanuskodi, S. (2019). The research output of ICAR-Indian Institute of horticultural research: A scientometric study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, *2019*.